

2021 University Research Symposium

Natural Hazards and Disasters Resilient Design Panel

Resource Document

Moderator: [Gavin Smith](#), Professor, College of Design ([View Slides](#), [View Video](#))

Panelists

- [Mohammed Gabr](#), Professor, College of Engineering
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

 - [Natalie Nelson](#), Assistant Professor, College of Agriculture and Life Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

 - [Andy Fox](#), Professor, College of Design
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
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Event Description:

With hurricanes, extreme temperature swings and other severe weather affecting the state more frequently each year, Eastern and coastal North Carolina is in the crosshairs of climate change as much as just about anywhere in the world. This panel discusses the ways NC State University experts in civil engineering, landscape architecture and land-use planning work to assist some of the communities that have been hit the hardest — from Lumberton to Princeville to Kitty Hawk — by helping design infrastructure that's more resilient to natural disasters.

You can [watch](#) the discussion in its entirety on the NC State Research YouTube channel.

Online Resources Shared:

- Learn more about I See Change: <https://www.iseechange.org/>
- Learn more about Natalie Nelson's Biosystems Analytics Lab: <http://nelson.rbind.io>

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- NC State Coastal Dynamics Design Lab:
<https://www.coastaldynamicsdesignlab.com/>
 - Recent N&O article underscoring needs of small NC communities:
<https://amp-newsobserver-com.cdn.ampproject.org/c/s/amp.newsobserver.com/news/politics-government/article250030879.html>
 - Another great citizen science precedent for gathering data:
<https://www.vims.edu/kingtide/>
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The following questions were answered live during the 2021 University Research Symposium Natural Hazards and Disasters Resilient Design Panel. Under each question, we provide links you can use to jump directly to the point in the video recording where the question was asked.

How does non-stationarity impact the design or even retrofiting of resilient infrastructure?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

How has the community responded to you coming in, as an “outsider” to inform design decisions, and have you ever received a kickback or resistance?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

What is data scarcity and what is the method you use to address it?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

How does non-stationary affect the search for a baseline?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

What are some of the obstacles to creating “disaster-proof” structures?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

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**How are you getting a team together that is constantly going after these grants?
How do you make the time? How do you build a team that can do this? How do
you go after grants for other people? How do you pull that off?**

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

**Do any of you work with undergraduate engineering student teams to create
technologies or systems to help the research or data collection automation?**

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

Are you working with our undergraduates?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)